

MAGISTRLAR CERTIFICATE

OF ACHIEVEMENT

R.A.P

Best
AWARD

... PROUDLY ...
PRESENTED TO

Sh. I. Shokirov

O'ZBEK TILIDA "BOYLIK VA KAMBAG'ALLIK" KONSEPTINING

LEKSIKSEMANTIK VA KOGNITIV XUSUSIYATLARI

WEBSITE: WWW.REANDPUB.UZ

EMAIL: INFO@REANDPUB.UZ

2023/MAY

zenodo